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“Effect of "Bacteria Game" on consolidation of knowledge in medical bacteriology and antibiotic therapy from the perspective of medical students”

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Type: Oral Presentation

“Impact of COVID-19 and lockdown-related mental health issues on learning performance in medical education”

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Type: Oral Presentation

“The Faculty Mentors’ Perceptions towards Portfolio in Undergraduate Medical Curriculum at Tbilisi Medical Academy in Georgia”

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Effect of "Bacteria Game" on consolidation of knowledge in medical bacteriology and antibiotic therapy from the perspective of medical students

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Background

Insufficient knowledge of bacteria and rational antibiotic therapy is one of the major causes of the misuse of antibiotics and development of resistance to them. Tbilisi Medical Academy piloted a gaming approach to stimulate consolidation of knowledge about bacteria and antibiotics by using the innovative approach - "Bacteria Game". We were introduced to the "Bacteria Game" by our French colleagues at AMEE-2022 conference. Study aimed to find out the effect of the game approach on consolidation of knowledge about bacteria and antibiotics from students' perspective.

Summary of Work

38 medical students (after the Bacteriology Course) were involved in the study. The Principle of the game - is to associate cards with the fun images of bacteria with rational antibiotic therapy and main resistances to antibiotics. The game was performed in groups, under the supervision of clinical microbiologist. A qualitative approach was applied where a five-point unipolar response questionnaire was filled out by the students. The number of participants in the survey is 29 (from 38).

Summary of Results

Most (89,5%) of the students think, that the Bacteria Game, is a useful tool for the organization of knowledge regarding bacteria and antibiotics and it helps in discovering

their own educational needs. 89,5% of the students agreed that the game allows for immediate feedback on individual knowledge gaps. They found the game fun (78,9%), engaging (94,7%) and thought, similar educational games should be used frequently within curriculum (89,5%).

Discussion and Conclusion

Educational Game after the completion of the Bacteriology course helps students to consolidate their knowledge about bacteria and rational antibiotic therapy, to identify gaps in their knowledge in a funny way and receive immediate feedback. Further research with similar games after the courses of Bacteriology, Pharmacology, Infectious Diseases, with the identification of retention rate of knowledge, will be interesting to evaluate the impact of gaming approach on consolidation of the knowledge about bacteria and antibiotics and also to evaluate the effect of Game as an integration tool between preclinical and clinical courses.

Take-home Message

Bacteria Game helps students to consolidate knowledge about bacteria and rational antibiotic therapy, to identify gaps in knowledge and receive immediate feedback.

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Impact of COVID-19 and lockdown-related mental health issues on learning performance in medical education

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Background

Around the world, one of the greatest challenges in recent years has been the Covid-19 pandemic. It has greatly impacted people's everyday lives including physical and mental health due to the damage caused by the viral infection as well as consequences of lockdowns. Based on the literature review and point of interest, we decided to study the influence of the Covid-19 pandemic and related mental health issues on the teaching performance of lecturers in medical universities alongside the study process of medical students.

Summary of Work

To discern how Covid-19 and lockdown-related mental health issues impacted teaching and study processes, a respective questionnaire has been elaborated. The survey was delivered online within two different universities – Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy (TMA) and Tbilisi State Medical University (TSMU).

Summary of Results

In total, 125 students and 25 lecturers participated in the survey. Responses reveal that Covid-19 has been diagnosed at least once in 19 lecturers (76%) and 49 students (43%), out of which 6 students (12%) admit having diagnosis of Covid-19 induced mental disorders.

In terms of teaching performance – 41% of lecturers admit that it has been affected and they have experienced teaching-related burnout during or since lockdown. It's notable that 25% of lecturers believe that the lockdown affected reaching the learning outcomes in the subjects which they lead.

As for learning – 42% of the students believe that their ability to retain information has worsened during/after lockdown and most of the reasons given are lack of concentration, relaxed mode or overuse of gadgets. 62% of the students get more tired while studying, in 72% the meantime of independent study has increased. Sleeping patterns have also changed (decreased) in 74%. As for reflection of findings on academic performance for 26% it has increased, for 44% it didn't change and for 30% it decreased.

Discussion and Conclusion

Apparently, the younger generation was more susceptible to Covid-19/Lockdown related mental health issues that affected their learning patterns, but had moderate influence on the academic performance.

Take-home Message

As lockdown-related mental health issues have affected learning patterns, that may lead to the need for different approaches to teaching

EPODFD1 (6341)

The Faculty Mentors' Perceptions towards Portfolio in Undergraduate Medical Curriculum at Tbilisi Medical Academy in Georgia

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Background

Portfolio is an important tool for coaching and assessing the authentic learning in undergraduate medical training and reflective ability is one of the main aspects of medical professionalism. Tbilisi Medical Academy in Georgia is in the process of piloting self-reflection as a mandatory part of student's portfolio. For reflective writing students are guided by the trained portfolio mentors who also deliver individual and group sessions with students. It's known that mentor-student relationship stimulates reflection more than portfolio itself, hence there's a huge responsibility on mentors who ensure effective portfolio.

Summary Of Work

The objective of this study was to determine the mentors' perceptions on the understanding of their role as a mentor, effectiveness of sessions from their perspective and importantly the impact on their own personal and professional development. In order to study the Mentors' perceptions and experiences mixed methods research was used, combining questionnaire consisting of 15 questions rated in a five-point Likert-type scale and face-to-face interviews in form of focus group meeting.

Summary Of Results

Seventeen mentors completed questionnaire and five of them participated in the focus group discussion. Majority of mentors agreed that they were provided sufficient training for portfolio session delivery and developing the reflective abilities of students was seen as one of the major roles. Mentors agreed that students could produce a piece of reflective writing well, however they felt unsure if students appreciated the structure of reflective learning and whether they recognized improvements in their practice. Mentors uniformly agreed that after portfolio sessions they can reflect more on their own personal development.

